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Brexit: Does it Pose a Multi-factorial Impact on Immigration and the UK Economy?

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to understand the impact of Brexit on immigration as well as on the UK economy. In the first part, immigration has been discussed as the strong background of the Brexit referendum. Immigration induced inconveniences along with the feeling of sovereignty intensified the call for the Brexit referendum. However, the major impact of Brexit (after the referendum) on immigration is the EU immigration trend tends to go down from 2016 to the present. The reason is probably a foretaste of the UK government to harden the immigration system for EU nationals through Brexit. A political uncertainty posed by the Brexit issue also fueled the unsteady situation in wage rate and demotivated the immigrants to stay in the UK or to immigrate there. In the meanwhile, the flow of Non-EU immigrants found its peak by rising to 379,000 in September 2019. The second part upholds that the UK economy is predicted to face a challenge to rejuvenate the economy after Brexit. It is found that the reduced immigration through Brexit notion may reduce the GDP of the UK by a significant percentage for a long time after Brexit. Moreover, it compresses the size of the labor force in the UK economy. For instance, EU and Non-EU nationals working in the UK increased meagerly since the referendum. The final part analyzes the policy decisions after Brexit and its impact on future immigration. Analyses show that Britain is probably going to attract mainly the high skilled immigrants through introducing a point-based immigration system. As a result, Brexit will be fruitful for the UK in making opportunities for innovation and invention in science, health, and technology by skilled immigrants. However, it will harm the rights of the EU immigrants especially those who are low skilled workers. As the UK is passing the transition period, there is time and scope to customize the settings of legislation through negotiations and policy deployment. Such steps will destine the fate of immigrants from the EU and Non-EU countries in the post Brexit era.

INTRODUCTION

After four years of the referendum on Brexit, finally, the UK has implemented its departure from the EU on 31st January 2020. One of the influencing factors behind the Brexit urge was the native's dissatisfaction with the migrants' influx as the refugee crisis culminated the then time (Parker, 2017). Taking back control from Europe was one of the stated motivations of Brexit (Young, 2017). In 2019, around 520,000 people settled permanently in the UK (OECD, 2019). Labour mobility and

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such migration opportunity among the member states work as a bolstered pillar of regional co-operation and integration. However, the UK, leaving the EU, may pressurize the other member states to take the brunt of huge migrants and asylum seekers. As a result, the effect of migration and immigration on both the UK and the EU can turn a new leaf that is depending on the UK preferences of new migration policies induced by Brexit.

However, the effect does not end here, as the impact of unrestricted immigration falls on the economic phenomena (Jafari and Britz, 2017; Simionescu et al., 2017). For instance, Brexit implementation is the mechanism to restrict the immigration of unskilled workers. In 2018, the approximate unskilled immigrant from the EU was 1 million (MacKinnon, 2018). If the number doubles, the wage of unskilled workers will fall by 4 percent (MacKinnon, 2018). Moreover, a long term effect may fall on the wage rate as the jobs in many public services will demand low skilled immigrants at lower wages (Wadsworth et al., 2016).

This paper seeks to realize the impact of Brexit on immigration and the UK economy. Notably, the UK is now passing the transition period and meanwhile, it remains in the customs unions. As a result, the restriction on immigration and labor mobility is not literally harshened. In this circumstance, the paper sets the objective to perceive whether any significant change in migration and the UK economy has happened. We, therefore, attempted to reach the objective by analyzing the immigration data and literatures during Brexit period and by discussing immigration related prediction based on the policy proceedings of the UK.

The paper parts three discussions to uphold the impact from different angles. The first part analyzes immigration as an influencing factor of Brexit and how Brexit influenced immigration. This part also narratively explains the situation of immigration from the EU and Non-EU countries after the Brexit referendum. The second part presents how Brexit induced immigration can impact the UK economy. In this section, welfare analysis, labor migration, and employment of immigrants and the UK nationals during the pre-Brexit and post-Brexit era are highlighted. The final part tells about the future immigration policy decision and its probable impact on immigration as part of Brexit implementation.

Methods and Data Dealings

This study is an exploratory type of research by which we tried to uphold the multifactorial impact of Brexit on immigration and the UK economy. To meet the objective, we gathered data from secondary sources like the ONS labor force survey, Migration Observatory (University of Oxford), the UK policy paper, and many journal articles. We assembled the data and information regarding migration, immigration, GDP, labor force supply, wage rate, and immigration policy notes in an MS Excel file. To compare the immigration scenario between the recent flow and the previous flow, we took some data from 1999 to 2019. In some cases, we sorted the data from 2009 to 2019, especially to exhibit the impact on immigration. We sorted and shaped all the data and made trend analyses by depicting line graphs and tables to show the influence of Brexit on immigration and the UK economy. In the process of finding economic impact, we categorized the gathered data into three sections i.e., welfare analysis, labor force condition, and wage. Welfare is measured in terms of GDP which is analyzed based on the current literatures. Most of the authors of the chosen literatures applied CGE- Computable General Equilibrium approach. This approach is known for the estimation of economic impact related to any change in policy and indicator. Thus we showed the extent of impact of immigration policy on the GDP of the UK.

Results and Discussion

Impact on Immigration from different Dimensional Era

Immigration as a Strong Background and Foreground of Brexit

The UK Independence Party (UKIP) pioneered the break of migration from the EU to the UK. The reason was the emergence of a feeling of sovereignty among the UK nationals. It emerged because of the immigration of the EU nationals under the EU free-movement policy. From a decade ago, EU migration was increasing at an alarming rate besides the migration of non-EU nationals.

Nearly 3.7 million EU nationals were living in the UK and all were immigrants in early 2017 (Vargas-Silva, Carlos. 2017). Gradually, the British citizens who could foresight the further flow of EU nationals, they solidified their 'we feelings' as part of sovereignty. Thus invocation of sovereignty and immigration-related inconveniences propelled to go for such voting for Brexit (Goodwin and Milazzo, 2017; Gordon, 2016). Basically, the natives strengthened the background of Brexit by feeling out of sorts for the unregulated inflow of immigrants. They eventually envisaged that they could face inaccessibility to better medical facilities, educational advantages, public services, and better jobs. Thus immigration in the UK intensified the call for such a referendum to leave the EU. The foreground of Brexit is to solidify the sovereignty.

Besides, the UK government is determined to rejuvenate its economy through an autonomous decision on economic phenomena. Therefore, immigration is not only the central issue for leaving the EU but also the mechanism for the future planning of the economy through impacting immigration. The supporters think that Brexit will bring gains for the UK nationals in employment by stemming the immigration and lessening the job competition. The British Prime Minister, in December 2019, hinted that unskilled and low skilled immigrants will not be able to be permanent residents of the UK and they will be offered for limited workplaces where labor crisis appears.⁴ According to The Telegraph (2020), after Brexit, the government will proceed to take action against illegal immigrants from 2022.

Migration Scenario during Brexit Era

After 2016, the year of the referendum, the major impact on migration is that the two trends find different directions (Figure 1). Before the referendum, the net migration has increased over time. Figure 1 certifies the decreasing trend after 2016. On the contrary, the Non-EU net migration follows the increasing trend after the referendum. Many reasons have worked behind the scene. The immigrants who are mostly workers, students, and asylum seekers understood the Brexit notion. According to the ONS report⁵, immigration to the UK is increasing from outside the EU for study reasons. ONS data also reveal that the flow of Non-EU immigrants found its peak by rising to 379,000 in September 2019. Non-EU immigration has reached its highest level since 2009 as the Non-EU net migration line also shows its peak in September 2019 (Figure 1).

Before one year of the referendum, EU nationals were almost 212,000 which reduces to 64,000 in September of last year (Figure 1). The number of immigrants from EU8 countries is also decreasing gradually (BBC, 2019). The reason for such a decrease in immigration from the EU may be the foretaste of the UK government for hardening the immigration system for EU nationals through Brexit. Regarding this issue, Madeleine Sumption⁶ thinks that the political uncertainty for the Brexit issue decreased the pound value which in turn demotivated the workers to stay and to immigrate in the UK.

Thus Brexit played the major role to stem the increasing trend of the EU net migration (Figure 1). However, Conservative Party driven government vowed to restrict net migration to less than 10,000.

⁴ The statement can be found at : <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/politics/2019/12/07/boris-johnson-unveils-strict-limits-unskilled-migrants/>

⁵ The data is available

at <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/internationalmigration/bulletins/migrationstatisticsquarterlyreport/february2020#eu-immigration-to-the-uk>

⁶ Madeleine Sumption, is the director of Migration Observatory at the University of Oxford, his statement is obtained from the website of BBC news at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-47400679>

The target is far away to fulfill, although Brexit has made it possible to formulate a new immigration system.

Figure 1: Net Migrations to the UK before and after Brexit Referendum

Source: Author's compilation based on the data of ONS-Labour Force Survey, 2019

Impact on Immigration before and after Brexit Vote

Portes and Forte (2017) argued that immigration from the EU has fallen for the uncertainty created in the political and social climate by Brexit. Although no laws and policies were set in motion from 2016 to 2019, the overall work-related immigration also declined significantly

(Figure 2). The work-related trend of immigration to the UK (Figure 2) reached a peak in the referendum year. Afterward, the trend tends to decline up to the final leave of the UK from the EU. The time between the vote and the final leave has shown that fewer workers arrived in the UK from the EU. From a peak of 190,000, in Figure 3, the number of EU nationals gathering for work in the UK has fallen to 79,000 which is the lowest since 2004 (ONS).

Eventually, the existing residents (the EU citizens) were doubtful about their rights in the UK because of forthcoming Brexit policies and immigration laws. Probably, fear blew in the mind of potentials immigrants also.

Thus, psychological factors along with Brexit driven force of uncertainty sharpened the lower arrivals of EU citizens (Portes and Forte, 2017).

Source: Authors' compilation based on the data of ONS- long term international migration

Figure 2: Total Immigration to the UK after and before Brexit Vote

Non-EU immigration increased slightly after the referendum (Figure 3). Figure 2 also delineates that the trend of study related immigration has been rising since the referendum. In 2011 (year ending to September), the study related immigration peaked to 246,000 and now the trend is moving towards the highest again after Brexit. When Political uncertainty and psychological factors created schizophrenia among the EU citizens to arrive in the UK for work-related reasons (Figure 3), the Non-EU nationals increasingly arrived in the UK for study benefits (Figure 2).

Source: Author's compilation based on the data of ONS-Labor Force Survey

Figure 3: Impact on EU and Non-EU Immigration for Work Related Reasons

Controlled Immigration through Brexit as an Impact on Economy

The last section dealt with the impact of Brexit on immigration. This phenomenon of influence can further affect the economy of the UK (Jafari and Britz, 2020). Portes (2016) predicted that the referendum would impact on immigration directly or indirectly through economic or other channels. Due to the Brexit-posed uncertainty, if the fall in migration continues and the rate decreases by 50 percent, the UK growth in productivity will reduce by 0.32 percent per annum (Boubtane et al., 2016). Furthermore, GDP will be 1.6 percent lower after a decade of Brexit than it would have been

otherwise (Wadsworth et al., 2016).

The UK will find economic loss in terms of the budget deficit as EU immigrants used to pay more taxes than they took out from the public service uses (Wadsworth et al., 2016). Wadsworth et al. (2016) also clarified that the inconveniences faced by UK nationals in jobs, wages, and public services were not for the EU immigrants. These adverse circumstances are the outcome of a massive economic crash that's effect has been prevalent for nearly 80 years or more. On the other hand, immigrants add value to the national welfare and help to bring positive changes in the economic outcome. To join this controversial issue, this study analyzes the impact on GDP and wages due to the reduced immigration through Brexit. We did not analyze the influence of Brexit on the UK economy broadly rather we discussed a straight impact on the UK GDP and wage due to the shrunk immigration posed by Brexit.

Impact of Brexit Induced Immigration on GDP

Most of the scholars showed that Brexit could be enacted either in a rigid or in a flexible way to deal with immigration. Table 1 shows the impact of the two ways of Brexit on GDP. If Brexit follows a hard manner, then the maximum of the authors found that the loss in terms of forgone GDP is higher compared to the flexible Brexit.

Table 1: Effect on the UK GDP due to Brexit Induced Change in Migration

Authors	Change in GDP ⁷ /Welfare through impacting migration/immigration	
	If Brexit is hard	If Brexit is flexible
Jafari and Britz (2020)	-2.49%	---
Jafari and Britz (2018)	-4.45%	---
Hosoe (2018)	-1.1%	---
Ortiz Valverde and Latorre (2020)	-1.60%	-0.95%
Valverde and Latorre (2020)	-0.17%	-0.08%
Valverde and Latorre (2017) ⁸	-0.55%	-0.35%
Coopers (2016)	-3.6%	-1.1%
Portes and Forte (2017)	-1.19%	-0.63%
Arregui and Chen (2018)	-7.8% to -5.2%	-3.9% to -2.6%

Source: Author's compilation based on the findings of literatures

The first three lists of authors (Table 1) show a highly negative impact of Brexit on GDP, when the Brexit is assumed to be hard compared to no Brexit. After all, the impact on GDP is clear by observing the negative signs before all of the percentages irrespective of the manner of Brexit i.e., hard or flexible for the immigrants (Table 1). In Table 1, the impact ranges from -7.8% to -0.17% if Brexit is hard. On the other hand, this range from -3.9% to 0.08% if Brexit is flexible.

Impact on Labour Availability, Productivity and Wage

We concluded the last section with a major finding that there is a loss in the UK GDP due to the reduced immigration. Moreover, Boubtane et al. (2016) found that if the share of migrants in the working-age population increases by one percentage point, then productivity will rise by 0.5 percent in the United Kingdom. It is assumed that a gradual decrease in the labor force due to a fall in immigration will cause the UK to lose productivity.

⁷ Maximum of the findings have been found applying CGE- Computable General Equilibrium approach by different studies. This approach is known for the estimation of economic impact related to any change in policy and indicator.

⁸ Valverde and Latorre (2017) showed that if immigration policy affects skilled labour migration then the loss is -0.55 percent and it is -1.1 percent if the policy affects (reduce) unskilled labour.

For instance, Arregui, and Chen (2018) reported that productivity will reduce by almost 0.6 percent in 2030 under the FTA scenario. The alarming rate of productivity loss is not the only effect of reduced migration.

It impacts wages too. The poorer UK nationals will be affected much if Brexit allows low skilled immigration (MacKinnon, 2018). It is assumed that if consumer price rises, then the low skilled immigrants whose earnings are also lower, may be affected by a reduction in real wages (MacKinnon, 2018). The scholars often argue that there will be less availability of skilled and semi-skilled immigrants (workers) after provision of a point-based immigration system. Therefore, the economy will have to struggle to replace the jobs which were previously occupied by the low and semi-skilled immigrants. For instance, the UK has also a possibility to face a labor shortage in hospitality and construction work of the UK. In this regard, Jafari and Britz (2020) opined that the negative impact can be mitigated if policy measures follow the way of increasing labor force participation and flow of immigration of workers

Table 2: Increase in Employment by Nationals in the UK since Referendum

Nationals working in the UK	Increased employment by thousand up to December 2019
UK	881,000
EU	71,000
Non-EU	111,000

Source: Author's compilation based on the data of ONS-Labor Force Survey

The Brexit issue changed the scenario of participation in the UK labor force (Table 2). Probably, the UK has been able to penetrate the Brexit notion in the employment system and has been able to change the immigration scenario. Therefore, most of the engagements have been secured by the UK nationals since the Brexit vote (employment increased by 881,000). In contrast, the number of EU nationals working in the UK has increased by only 71,000 since 2016 (Table 2). The difference is vivid during the era of 2016-2019. The Non-EU nationals working in the UK have increased in this era by 111,000 which is larger than the increase for EU nationals. Figure 4 attests this claim by showing the trend of Non-EU national's employment rising.

Figure 4 also shows that the number of EU nationals who work in the UK has increased gradually over time. Since 1999, the trend of EU national employment has gone up. However, when the Brexit issue rose, from 2016, the trend gets flattered meaning that the increase of employment of EU nationals has risen meagerly. But ONS data⁹ claim that EU nationals working in the UK have increased by 36,000 to 2.31 million from 2018 to 2019.

Where, only 17 percent of the employed workers were outside the UK in 2018. Likewise, in Figure 4, the Non-EU employment trend seems stable.

The employment trend of Non-EU immigrants (Figure 4) is on starting to rise after the referendum. Thus Brexit changed the employment scenario of the UK reducing the rate of employment of EU nationals.

⁹ The data is available at-

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/articles/ukandnonukpeopleinthelabourmarket/february2020>

Source: Author’s compilation based on the data of ONS - Labor Force Survey

Figure 4: Employment Scenario of EU and Non-EU Nationals in the UK

The unemployment rate in Figure 5 shows that the trends are downward near to 2019. The unemployment trend of the UK and the EU nationals is very intimate as both have crossed each other several times since 1999. It indicates that the unemployment rate of the two nationals is almost similar and even in the Brexit era. The trend of unemployment rate linked with Non-EU nationals is consistently higher since 1999. Therefore, they are the most sufferer.

Source: Author’s compilation based on the data of ONS - Labor Force Survey

Figure 5: Unemployment Rate for EU, Non-EU, and the UK Nationals

Policy Decision and Effect on Future Immigration

Portes (2016) claimed that two main issues will be prominent in the UK after Brexit. The first one is whether a new system after Brexit will keep some measures of preference for EU nationals. The second thing is the policy whether it will advance to a restrictive or flexible direction. In the meanwhile, the right of existing immigrants from the EU is a widespread concern and it will be a matter of negotiation between the EU and the UK. House of Lords (2017) optioned that the negotiation process could expedite the immigration from the EU by allowing free movement with a job offer. However, in the case of a point-based new immigration system, highly skilled workers will be able to come to the UK without any job offer. In this context, citizens from the EU and the non-EU countries will enjoy the same opportunities. The immigration system can be designed in such a way that the medium and low skilled migrants can find a route (Owen, 2017). Owen (2017) also stated referred a report that 75 percent of the EU nationals living in the UK will be disqualified under the present Non-EU visa rules. Besides, the requirements of the English language and minimum income could bring precariousness to the EU and Non-EU immigration. To what extent the new immigration system will impact on the EU and the Non-EU immigration will depend on the policy and negotiations.

The UK government's policy paper¹⁰ points out that the UK is advancing to initiate an immigration bill which will be a point-based system. This system is purposive to absorb the high skilled workers. Moreover, this system will treat the EU and Non-EU nationals equally from the starting of 2021. Then migrants will have to pay a certain amount of fee against study and work-related visas. This system will allow to tighten the border security also. However, there are availability of time and scope for fruitful negotiations regarding the fate of the current and the future EU and Non-EU immigrants. After all, if immigration decisions get tighter, it should be a gradual process so that the economy will face less harm (Valverde and Latorre, 2019).

Discussion: Impact on Immigration from the Negative Perspective

The post-Brexit immigration system focuses on the immigration of skilled EU workers. If this system is maintained in a hard manner, the right of the existing low skilled EU workers may be affected. According to Munyama (2019)¹¹, they can be deprived of the right to work, return, and the right to social security. The fear escalates since 'The Charter of Fundamental Rights' of the EU will no longer be a part of the UK law after the implementation period (Barnard, 2019).

Moreover, Brexit may push up an enforced return at the border. There is a possibility that Border control after 2020, it will dwarf the right of immigrants especially the asylum seekers. However, the impact on the EU students is ambiguous, especially those who want to study in the UK from 2021. It is assumed in the new system that the EU students have to apply for a UK student visa like other international students. Service sector may experience a shortage of staffs and workers if there are harder rules in the Visa process by the British Government. Besides, construction and other promising sectors in the UK will suffer from a shortage of labour if the new immigration system deters the inflow of low or semi-skilled workers truly. Furthermore, Brexit

¹⁰ The information is collected from the policy paper titled "The UK's points-based immigration system: policy statement". The note is available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-uks-points-based-immigration-system-policy-statement/the-uks-points-based-immigration-system-policy-statement>

¹¹ Killion Munyama (2019). The implications of Brexit for migration, Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe. Available at: <http://www.assembly.coe.int/LifeRay/MIG/Pdf/TextesProvisoires/2019/20191203-BrexitMigration-EN.pdf>

may affect the UK economy because of reformation after rolling new policies and measures to control immigration. The reason for such an impact can be apprehended by observing graphs in the first part. The graphs showed that the inflow of workers from the EU and outside the EU is decreasing after the referendum. Reformation and replacement by provisioning new policies with the decreased labour force will take a huge time.

Discussion: Impact on Immigration from the Positive Perspective

Brexit brings about a positive change in the UK territory. Sovereignty was the dogmata to make Brexit successful. Undoubtedly, sovereignty is bolstered by restricting immigration. In this regard, the UK will be free to make trade deals and migration policy. Most importantly, the UK will gain the space of enjoying the freedom of authority to formulate the migration policy without any interference of the EU legislations and authority.

Mainly, the fundamental principle of Brexit is to revive the UK parliamentary sovereignty and to regain the law-making powers (Young, 2017). Another benefit the UK will enjoy is avoidance of discomfort in housing and in services made by the gathering of immigrants. Besides, a huge reduction in immigration will allow Britain to shape their demographic pyramid. Brexit will impact on the technology, research, and service sectors such that more skilled and chosen immigrants will be engaged in those sectors. Optimistically, innovation and invention by such potential immigrants will take the country in the new direction of research, technology, and trade. This can happen if Brexit facilitates the way of skilled manpower inflow in the immigration system.

Conclusion

This paper firstly pointed out the evolution of Brexit, the referendum, and the final leave of the UK from the EU. The paper shows immigration was a strong background of Brexit and still it remains in the central thinking of Brexit implementation. Afterward, the rest of the parts in this paper adumbrated the impact of Brexit on immigration from various dimensions. Brexit notion helped to decrease the flow of the EU migrants in the UK. However, the inflow of migrants from the countries outside the EU has risen dramatically in the UK although a significant percentage of these migrants are students. A major impact is- the UK faces the unimaginative fall in immigrants who mainly come for work-related reasons in the UK. The consequent results impact the labor force and output of the UK economy. Moreover, literatures predict that reduced immigration through Brexit will reduce the UK economy severely in terms of foregone GDP and welfare. Eventually, the economy will experience a reduction of GDP by a significant percentage in 2030. Moreover, the construction and service sector in the UK will be at risk in the sense of suffering from low skilled and semi-skilled labour shortage at a lower wage. Many challenges are related to the migration dealings which will be prominent in the policy and negotiations. However, in the path of Brexit implementation, the UK is signaling to launch a point-based immigration system by deploying new legislation. The policy recommendation of the MAC (Migration Advisory Committee) suggests that this system vanishes the free movement advantage in the UK. As a result, the EU citizens will find it difficult to regain their entitlements and rights. To what extent the right of immigrants will be maintained or minimized is depending on the mitigation and intensification of hardness in the post-Brexit immigration system. Therefore, policy debate implicated with the right of current EU immigrants in the UK as well as the future immigrants may be a concern in the negotiation table. The concern is also for those who are eligible to be permanent residents as per the current visa rules. However, Brexit has already benefitted the UK nationals.

For example, UK nationals are taking up the job places increasingly more than the immigrants are (around 881,000 engagements for UK nationals were in the last year). Furthermore, a good hope in the controlled immigration through Brexit is- the UK will employ and hail more skilled immigrants who can contribute to the science, technology, and research to boost up the economy.

The UK nationals have strengthened their feeling of sovereignty keeping trust on Brexit such that the UK government will be able to reframe its trade deals, migration, and internal deals without any interference of the EU legislation.

Thus the impact of Brexit on immigration is multifarious. But how Brexit will allow or restrict immigration to tackle the negative impact is the matter of policy decisions and negotiations between the UK and EU. Only then the true impact of Brexit implementation on immigration can be perceived in the post-Brexit era.

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